

1 **Title:** Look-up and look-down neurons in the mouse visual thalamus during freely moving
2 exploration

3 **Authors:** Patrycja Orłowska-Feuer¹, Aghileh S. Ebrahimi¹, Antonio G. Zippo², Rasmus S.
4 Petersen¹, Robert J. Lucas¹, Riccardo Storchi^{1*#}

5
6 ¹ University of Manchester,
7 Faculty of Biology, Medicine and Health,
8 School of Biological Science,
9 Division of Neuroscience and Experimental Psychology,
10 Oxford Road,
11 M139PL, Manchester,
12 United Kingdom

13
14 ² Institute of Neuroscience
15 Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche,
16 Via Raoul Follereau, 3
17 20854, Vedano al Lambro,
18 Italy
19

20 **Correspondence:** riccardo.storchi@manchester.ac.uk

21 *Lead Contact; #Corresponding Author
22

23 **Twitter Handle:** <https://twitter.com/riccardostorch1>
24

25 **Summary**

26

27 Visual information reaches cortex via the thalamic dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus (dLGN).
28 dLGN activity is modulated by global sleep/wake states and arousal, indicating that it is not
29 simply a passive relay station. However, its potential for more specific visuomotor
30 integration is largely unexplored. We addressed this question by developing robust 3D video
31 reconstruction of mouse head and body during spontaneous exploration, paired with
32 simultaneous neuronal recordings from dLGN. Unbiased evaluation of a wide range of
33 postures and movements revealed a widespread coupling between neuronal activity and
34 few behavioural parameters. In particular, postures associated with the animal looking
35 up/down correlated with activity in >50% neurons and the extent of this effect was
36 comparable to that induced by full body movements (typically locomotion). By contrast,
37 thalamic activity was minimally correlated with other postures or movements (e.g. left/right
38 head and body torsions). Importantly, up/down postures and full body movements were
39 largely independent and jointly coupled to neuronal activity. Thus, while most units were
40 excited during full body movements, some expressed highest firing when the animal was
41 looking up (“look-up” neurons) while others when the animal was looking down (“look-
42 down” neurons). These results were observed in the dark, thus representing a genuine
43 behavioural modulation, and were amplified in a lit arena. Our results demonstrate that the
44 primary visual thalamus, beyond global modulations by sleep/awake states, is potentially
45 involved in specific visuomotor integration, and reveal two distinct couplings between
46 up/down postures and neuronal activity.

47

48 **Keywords:** visual thalamus, dorsal Lateral Geniculate Nucleus, neural coding, freely moving,
49 exploratory behaviours, 3D reconstruction, Statistical Shape Models, neuromodulation

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51

52

53 **Introduction**

54 A key role of vision is to guide motor actions¹⁻⁴. In turn, motor actions modify the visual
55 experience through self-motion and changes in head and body postures so that appropriate
56 interpretation of incoming visual information depends on these parameters⁵⁻⁷. For example,
57 mice respond with freezing to a sweeping object flying overhead² but with pursuit hunting
58 to a similar object moving at ground level³, suggesting that selection of the appropriate
59 action requires integration of head and body positioning with the visual input. This process
60 of integration has traditionally been studied at high levels of the hierarchical visual pathway
61 (e.g. Posterior Parietal Cortex:^{8,9}; rodent Lateral Posterior Thalamus and primate Pulvinar:
62^{10,11}). Spontaneous and visually evoked activity in primary visual cortex has also been shown
63 to be strongly affected by locomotion in head-fixed preparations¹²⁻¹⁵ and head rotations
64 along different axes in freely moving animals^{16,17}.

65 The role of primary visual thalamus in integrating the visual input with postures and
66 movements is still unresolved. The traditional view of primary visual thalamus is that of a
67 relay station between the retina and cortex. However, retinal input only represents a small
68 fraction of the afferent synapses^{18,19} and other brain projections, arising from brainstem,
69 visual cortex and thalamic reticular nucleus, can influence the flow of visual information
70^{18,20,21}. A vast body of work has shown that spontaneous and evoked patterns of firing
71 activity (e.g. tonic or bursting) and the gain of visual responses are determined according to
72 anaesthesia, sleep and awake states (see e.g.²²⁻²⁶). It has also been shown that neurons in
73 visual thalamus (and even in the retina^{27,28}) are modulated by locomotion in a head fixed
74 preparation^{29,30}. However, since in this preparation locomotion is strongly associated with
75 arousal²⁷⁻²⁹, it is not clear whether such modulation reflects a generalised state of alertness
76 or a specific effect of locomotion. Most importantly, a description of which postures and
77 movements modulate neuronal activity in natural unconstrained conditions is still missing.
78 The primary goal of this study was to address this deficit by measuring simultaneously
79 postures, movements and firing activity in the primary visual thalamus in freely moving
80 mice.

81 Success of this endeavour is dependent upon a method to accurately quantify the wide
82 repertoire of postures and movements available to freely moving mice. Computational
83 methods to track body parts in 3D and use these to reconstruct pose at frame-by-frame
84 resolution are increasingly available³¹⁻³⁴. We have previously developed such an approach
85 suitable for mice³⁴ and here we extend it to measure a wide variety of 3D movements and
86 postures. We find that the higher dimensional description of behaviour enabled by this
87 approach is key to understanding motor influences on the early visual system. Thus, while
88 we confirm that high levels of motor activity (including but not limited to the locomotion
89 available to head fixed animals) excites the primary visual thalamus, we find that head and
90 body postures are at least as influential in defining neuronal activity in this region.
91 Moreover, while movement provides a general increase in firing, the impact of postures is
92 more specific, with a subset of neurons excited by poses characterised by looking upwards
93 (“look-up” neurons), while a different set are excited by poses associated with looking
94 downwards (“look-down” neurons). Our discovery, that electrophysiological activity in the

95 primary visual thalamus is influenced by posture during natural exploration, raises the
96 possibility that thalamic processing of visual information can be flexibly modulated
97 according to specific visuomotor behaviours.

98 **Results**

99 **Spontaneous exploration in freely moving animals is defined by independent sets of** 100 **postures and movements**

101 Mice were recorded by using four synchronized cameras (Figure S1A) during spontaneous
102 exploration of an open field arena either in the dark or under steady illumination
103 (respectively n = 11, 8 animals). To capture posture and movements in freely moving mice
104 we first performed 3D reconstruction of head and body in animals implanted with
105 multichannel microelectrodes (STAR Methods) in dorsal Lateral Geniculate Nucleus (dLGN).
106 Eleven landmarks were identified on the mouse's body and microelectrode head-stage and
107 were used for tracking the animals (Figure 1A). The 2D tracking data were then triangulated
108 to generate an initial 3D reconstruction of the animal (STAR Methods). Outliers and missing
109 data in the 3D reconstruction were then corrected by extending a previously developed
110 approach³⁴ (STAR Methods). The corrected 3D data provided a robust estimate of the
111 animal body over time (Video S1).

112 From the 3D reconstruction, we quantified the postures and movements of the mouse in
113 terms of fourteen behavioural variables. Hereafter we will define this set of variables as the
114 behavioural state of the animal. Head postures were quantified by head elevation and
115 left/right angles (Figure 1B, Video S2; Hel: head elevation; Hlr: head left/right). Full-body
116 postures were quantified by projection on the first 3 eigenposes (Figure 1B, Video S2; Bar:
117 body arch; Blr: body left/right bend; Blu: body lunge), sufficient to explain 80% of changes in
118 the body shape, and by rearing (Figure 1B, Video S2; Re: Rearing). Six movements were
119 quantified by the temporal derivative of the above postures (dHel, dHlr, dBar, dBlr, dBlu,
120 dRe). Locomotion was quantified by speed of movement on the x-y plane of the arena
121 (Figure 1B, Video S2; Lc: locomotion). Finally, we quantified overall motion (Figure 1B; OM:
122 overall motion) by measuring the 3D Euclidean distance between all body points in
123 consecutive frames.

124 Given biomechanical constraints we expect some postures and movements to correlate with
125 each other. Therefore, we set out to identify relevant groupings among behavioural state
126 variables. To do that we first applied Mutual Information to quantify linear and nonlinear
127 correlations between all pairs. This analysis revealed two main groups that corresponded to
128 postures and movements respectively (Figure 1C). The existence of these two groups was
129 confirmed by a hierarchical clustering analysis (Figure 1D, High HL partition). Hierarchical
130 clustering also revealed that, at a finer grain of analysis, there were three prominent sub-
131 groups (Figure 1D, Low HL partition). (1) Head elevation, body arch and rearing were all
132 associated with animal looking up or down and therefore we defined this group as up/down
133 postures (Figure 1D, UD). (2) Left/right head turn and left/right body bend, that we defined
134 altogether as left/right postures (Figure 1D, LR). (3) Overall motion and locomotion defined
135 hereafter as full body movements (Figure 1D, FB). The same sub-groups were observed both
136 in the dark and under ambient illumination (Figure S1B-E), indicating that these sub-groups
137 represent a stable and robust feature of mouse behaviour. Other subgroups were also

138 identified (e.g. dHlr and dBlr, Figure 1D), however these were not consistent across dark and
139 ambient illumination (Figure S1B-E).

140 Visual inspection indicated that individual variables within each subgroup, although
141 correlated, captured distinct components of the mouse behaviour (see representative times
142 series in Figure S2A,B). Thus, body arch and head elevation typically preceded rearing
143 (Figure S2C). Changes in head posture, captured by head elevation and head left/right turns,
144 could also occur with reduced or minor changes in full body posture, captured by body arch
145 and body left/right bend (Figure S2D,E). Overall motion, while strongly associated with
146 locomotion, also encompassed vertical actions like rearing (Figure S2F).

147

148 **Upward/downward facing postures and full body movements dominate firing rate** 149 **modulation in visual thalamus in the dark**

150 We set out to determine the extent to which behavioural state variables involved in
151 spontaneous exploratory behaviour were coupled to neuronal activity. In order to eliminate
152 the possibility that such couplings could arise from associations between behaviour and
153 visual experience, we first ran these recordings in the dark (see Figure S3A,B for mean and
154 peak firing rates for single units in this dataset).

155 From simple visual inspection we observed that some units exhibited an increase or
156 decrease in firing that accompanied step changes in behavioural state variables (Figure
157 2A,B). Joint visualization of behavioural time series and spike patterns also suggested an
158 association between behavioural variables and spiking activity (Figure 2C,D).

159 To quantify these effects, we performed a cross-correlation analysis between individual
160 variables and single unit firing rates that revealed that a large fraction of units exhibited
161 significant cross-correlation peaks (Figure 2E; shuffle test, STAR Methods). The most
162 common correlations were with variables encompassing up/down postures and full body
163 movements (Figure 2E, UD & FB). For most variables, a comparable number of units
164 exhibited either positive or negative correlation peaks, while, for full body movements, units
165 exhibited almost exclusively positive correlations (Figure 2E). Across all variables the
166 correlation peaks occurred on average around time zero (see Figure 2F), indicating that this
167 aspect of neuronal activity neither systematically predicted nor lagged actions, but rather
168 provided a near instantaneous reflection of the behavioural state. Overall, >70% units
169 (n=69/96 units from 11 mice) were linearly correlated with up/down postures and/or full
170 body movements (Figure 2G) and the remaining units had no significant correlations with
171 any other variable. A coherence analysis further revealed that the linear coupling between
172 behavioural state variables and single unit activity was concentrated in the 0-2Hz range
173 (Figure 2H).

174 In order to capture both linear and nonlinear correlations between behavioural state
175 variables and neuronal activity we performed three types of additional analyses: first we
176 calculated Mutual Information (MI) between single variables and firing activity of individual

177 units (Figure 3A,B), then we performed cross-validated predictions of single unit firing from
178 individual variables (Figure 3A,C,D) and finally we applied the same predictive approach to
179 estimate single behavioural state variables from the firing rates of all the units that we
180 recorded simultaneously from individual animals (Figure 3E,F).

181 First, for each unit we identified the single behavioural state variable with highest Mutual
182 Information (corresponding to that unit's 'favoured' behavioural variable). Most units ($n =$
183 $80/96$ units from 11 mice) favoured variable was either with an up/down posture or a full
184 body movement (Figure 3A, UD and FB, solid colour bars). Among up/down postures, units
185 conveyed higher information for body arch than for rearing ($p = 0.0056$, sign = 62, $n = 96$
186 units from 11 mice, sign-test), while body arch and head elevation were not significantly
187 different ($p = 0.1253$, sign = 40, $n = 96$, sign-test). Among full body movements, information
188 conveyed by locomotion and overall motion were also comparable ($p = 0.36$, sign = 53, $n =$
189 96 units from 11 mice, sign-test). Across the recorded neuronal population, the amount of
190 information was proportional to the firing rate, so that units with higher firing rates carried
191 higher information (Figure 3B, $p < 0.0001$, $n = 96$ units from 11 mice, t-test). These results
192 indicate that the modulation of dLGN neurons by posture mainly reflected sensitivity to
193 body arch, which encompasses head elevation, while modulation by movements was
194 dominated by locomotion.

195 We then trained a model (based on XGBoost,^{35,36} STAR Methods) to predict firing rate from
196 individual behavioural variables. We evaluated prediction accuracy by calculating Pearson's
197 linear correlation between recorded and predicted spike-counts on cross-validated data.
198 Based on these results, for each unit we identified the best predictor, i.e. the variable
199 associated with highest Pearson's correlation. Across our dataset the best predictors
200 captured significant amounts of variability ($p = 0.16 \pm 0.08$, mean \pm SD; Figure 3C). To exclude
201 the possibility that this result was an artifact of our analyses, we shifted the behavioural
202 variables by half a recording epoch in order to break their associations with neuronal activity
203 while preserving their temporal structure (STAR Methods). Prediction accuracy dropped
204 indicating that our analyses capture genuine coupling between behavioural variables and
205 neuronal activity. (Figure S3C). Consistently with Mutual Information analyses, up/down
206 postures and full body movements were the best predictors for 76% of the units (Figure 3A,
207 striped bars) substantially outperforming left/right postures and all other variables (Figure
208 3D; $p < 0.0005$ across all comparisons, sign-test, $n = 96$ from 11 animals). Prediction accuracy
209 was also proportional to the units' firing rate ($p < 0.0001$, $n = 96$ from 11 animals, t-test).

210 Finally, we used the same XBG models to predict behavioural state variables from population
211 activity (i.e. the spike counts from all units that were simultaneously recorded from each
212 animal). We found that up/down postures and full body movements were the best predicted
213 variables, providing substantial increases in accuracy over left/right postures and other
214 variables (Figure 3E,F; $p = 0.0002$, $\chi^2 = 19.22$, $n = 11$ mice, Kruskal-Wallis test).

215 Overall, these results show that, during spontaneous exploration in the dark, neurons in
216 visual thalamus are modulated by behavioural state and the effect is associated with
217 upward/downward facing postures and full body movements.

218

219 **Single unit firing is jointly modulated by upward/downward facing postures and full body**
220 **movements in the dark**

221 Do individual units encode single behavioural variables do they encode more than one? To
222 answer this we first estimated Mutual Information between single unit activity and all
223 possible pairs of variables. For each unit we then selected the pair associated with the
224 highest information. We first asked whether pairs of variables provided more information
225 than individual ones. To provide the fairest comparison we re-estimated Mutual Information
226 for individual variables by using pairs in which the values from one variable were shuffled
227 over time in order to remove its association with neuronal activity (STAR Methods). We
228 found that most units conveyed more information about variable pairs than about individual
229 variables (Figure 4A, $p = 1 \cdot 10^{-8}$, sign-test, $n = 96$ units from 11 mice). This was the case also
230 when we compared average Mutual Information across animals ($p = 0.01$, sign-test, $n = 11$
231 animals). We next asked which variables were most strongly coupled to neuronal activity.
232 We found that pairwise combinations of up/down postures and full body movements
233 conveyed the highest Mutual Information (Figure 4B), providing, on average, a 90% increase
234 over other pairwise combinations that did not include those variables (Figure 4C).

235 Consistently with Mutual Information analyses, pairs of behavioural state variables provided
236 better prediction of single unit activity compared with single variables (Figure S3D-E; $p =$
237 $2 \cdot 10^{-14}$, sign-test, $n = 96$ units from 11 mice; the distribution of prediction accuracies is
238 reported in Figure 4D). Up/down postures and full body movements substantially
239 outperformed other predictors (Figure S3F).

240 Finally, we asked which and how many different types of modulations could be observed at a
241 single unit level. To answer this question we performed an unsupervised clustering analysis
242 (based on community detection³⁷, STAR Methods). Each unit was represented as a bivariate
243 histogram of the average firing rates as function of body arch and overall motion (the two
244 strongest predictors). The clustering process then automatically determined the number of
245 distinct types (STAR Methods). This analysis revealed two classes of units: “look-up” units,
246 most active when the animal assumed an upward facing posture (Figure 4E, left panel;
247 Figure 4F, top panel; $n = 52$ from 11 mice) and “look-down” units, most active when the
248 animal assumed a downward facing posture (Figure 4E, right panel; Figure 4F, bottom panel;
249 $n = 44$). Both “look-up” and “look-down” units were positively modulated by increased levels
250 of motor activity (Figure 4F; look-up: $p = 1 \cdot 10^{-37}$, $8 \cdot 10^{-12}$, $\chi^2 = 190.12$, 66.4; $n = 52$, 44;
251 Kruskal-Wallis test for look-up and look-down units). Similar clustering results were obtained
252 by combining overall motion with head elevation or rearing (Figure S3G-J).

253 These results show that dLGN units are jointly coupled to overall motion and up/down
254 postures, with ~%54 units most excited during upward facing postures and the remaining
255 fraction during downward facing postures.

256

257 **Modulation of single unit activity by behavioural state is maintained and amplified by**
258 **ambient illumination**

259 All modulations described so far were obtained by recording the animal in the dark, i.e. in
260 absence of visual stimulation. We next asked whether these modulations would persist
261 when the visual thalamus is additionally stimulated by visual inputs. To address this question
262 we repeated our freely moving experiments but this time with the arena illuminated (within
263 the photopic range, STAR Methods).

264 In the light arena average values of Mutual Information across all postures and movements
265 were higher than in the dark (Figure 5A, $p < 0.005$ for all variables, rank-sum tests, $n = 96$ and
266 75 units from 11 and 8 mice recorded respectively in for dark and light conditions). All other
267 results were qualitatively recapitulated. Up/down postures and full body movements were
268 still associated with largest Mutual Information values in the majority of the cells (81% , $n =$
269 $61/75$ units from 8 mice, Figure 5B). Most units conveyed more information about pairs of
270 behavioural state variables than about individual variables (Figure S4C, $p = 5 \cdot 10^{-11}$, sign = 65 ,
271 $n = 75$ units from 8 mice) and pairwise combinations of up/down postures and full body
272 movements conveyed the highest Mutual Information (Figure S4D,E). Results based on
273 predictive modelling approach were consistent with Mutual Information analysis (Figure 5C;
274 Figure S4F-J). Clustering analysis revealed two classes of units that qualitatively matched the
275 “look-up” and “look-down” units observed in the dark (Figure 5D,E)..

276 Finally, we asked whether individual neurons maintained the same tuning to behavioural
277 state variables in darkness and in light. In order to avoid potential artifacts due to electrode
278 movements across different days we analysed a dataset in which animals were recorded
279 both in dark and light within the same experimental session ($n = 58$ units from 5 mice). We
280 found that the tuning for the strongest predictors, body arch and overall movement, was
281 significantly preserved (Figure 5F,G).

282 These results show that the coupling between behavioural variables and single unit activity
283 described in the dark is maintained and amplified by visual stimulation.

284

285

286 **Discussion**

287 In everyday life, visual processing is concurrent with movements and changes in posture. It
288 follows that to understand visual processing, we also need to understand how specific
289 actions affect neuronal activity along the visual pathway. Previous studies found strong
290 modulations of neuronal activity by motor activity along the visual pathway and throughout
291 the brain ^{12-15,29,30,38,39}. However, since most studies were performed in head-fixed animals, it
292 is still unclear which aspects of behaviour would couple to neuronal activity in natural freely
293 moving conditions. Our study aimed to fill this gap in the mouse dLGN, the key subcortical
294 station linking the retina to the primary visual cortex.

295 Our first result was that upward and downward facing postures affected firing rate of >50%
296 of neurons in dLGN. Encoding of head and body postures was previously described in the rat
297 posterior parietal cortex and frontal motor cortex ⁴⁰ but, to the best of our knowledge, not in
298 conventional visual centres. Most of the studies on visual processing focussed on the effect
299 of locomotion on a treadmill and revealed that this behaviour substantially affect neuronal
300 activity in primary visual cortex (see e.g. ^{12-15,41}), and dLGN and LP regions of the visual
301 thalamus ^{29,30,42}. Since those studies were performed in head-fixed animals, the nature this
302 preparation did not allow for measuring head movements and head and body postures. Two
303 recent studies, performed in freely moving animals, quantified the effect of head
304 movements, but not of head and body postures, in primary visual cortex ^{16,17}. Our results
305 indicate that the effect of head movements (e.g. left-right head turns) on firing rates might
306 be present in dLGN but is significantly less prominent than the effect of upward and
307 downward facing postures (see e.g. Figure 3A).

308 Our second result was that the firing rate coupling to upward and downward facing postures
309 was largely independent from, and interacted with, the coupling to full body movements
310 (and typically locomotion). This result addresses a long-standing debate about the nature of
311 behavioural modulation in dLGN. Neuromodulation of primary visual thalamocortical loops
312 has been traditionally associated with the control of sleeping and arousal states ²⁶. More
313 recent studies have shown that modulation of neuronal activity in these regions is related to
314 both motor activity and arousal (as measured via pupil dilation) ^{27-29,43,44}. Separating the
315 arousal component from motor activity component has been traditionally difficult using
316 head-fixed preparations since locomotion on a treadmill is strongly coupled to pupil dilation
317 ^{27,29,44,45}. Thus, while intermediate levels of arousal can occur without locomotion ^{28,41,46,47},
318 locomotion always coincide with high pupil dilation ^{42,43,47}. Our experiments in freely moving
319 animals reveal two largely independent modulations, respectively by full body movements
320 and upward and downward facing postures. Thus, while locomotion was associated with a
321 generalised increased in firing rate concomitant with high arousal, this effect was gated by
322 upward and downward facing postures, so that some units were most active when animals
323 pointed their head high (“look-up” units), while others when animals kept their head low
324 (“look-down” units). This result indicates that neuronal modulation in dLGN can be
325 behavioural-specific (e.g. some neurons will be active while exploring the ground, others
326 while searching the sky) rather than simply reflecting a generalised state of arousal or motor

327 activity. Additional experiments in other primary sensory thalamic regions will be required
328 to understand whether these results also apply to other sensory modalities.

329 Our final result was that, when experiments were repeated in an illuminated environment,
330 the coupling of firing rate to postures and movements was maintained and amplified. The
331 most parsimonious explanation is that the amplification would arise from the introduction of
332 movement-related visual stimuli produced by self-motion. Alternatively, ambient light could
333 drive neuronal activity of the visual thalamus into a more excitable state ^{25,48-50} and this
334 could amplify the coupling observed in the dark. Finally, if the coupling between firing rates
335 and behaviour is inherited from the cortex, ambient light could modify the interactions
336 between excitatory and inhibitory populations in primary visual cortex ^{16,51} and, in turn, the
337 corticofugal feedback onto the visual thalamus.

338 The sources of coupling to the behavioural state on the primary visual thalamus are
339 currently unknown. Modulation by upward and downward facing postures could be
340 provided by vestibular afferents from the brainstem, since optogenetic stimulation of the
341 Medial Vestibular Nucleus diffusely excites sensory thalamic nuclei and cortices ⁵².
342 Consistently with this possibility, results from anaesthetized cats showed that visual
343 responses of >80% neurons in the dLGN were modulated by electrical stimulation of
344 vestibular nuclei in the brainstem ⁵³. Primary visual cortex could also play an important role,
345 by conveying both postural and motor information via the extensive direct and indirect (via
346 Thalamic Reticular Nucleus, TRN) corticofugal projections ¹⁸. Strong inputs from thalamic
347 regions other than TRN are unlikely given the sparse intra-thalamic connectivity ⁵⁴. Visual
348 thalamus has also been shown to receive afferents from the superior colliculus ²⁰ and
349 parabigeminal nucleus ²¹, two important regions involved in visuomotor behaviours and
350 action selection ⁵⁵. Additionally, direct or indirect input from the mesencephalic locomotor
351 region (Pedunculo Pontine Nucleus, Laterodorsal Tegmental Nucleus) could be involved ^{21,56}.
352 Finally, recent studies also provided evidence that arousal and locomotion modulate input
353 from the retinal afferents ^{27,28} and this modulation affects sensory processing in visual
354 thalamus. Further studies will be needed to investigate the relative contribution of those
355 sources.

356 Our results indicate that most neurons in visual thalamus are modulated according to
357 multiple components of the ongoing behaviour. This is consistent with recent studies of
358 brain-wide modulation in mouse and flies and worms (for a review see ⁵⁷), indicating that
359 spontaneous neuronal activity is high dimensional and captures many distinct components
360 of spontaneous behaviour. However a recent study compared the correlation between firing
361 rate and running in marmoset and mouse primary visual cortices and found significantly
362 smaller correlations in marmosets⁵⁸. We currently do not understand the functional role(s)
363 of brain-wide representation of behaviour. One possibility is that excitation of specific
364 subsets of neurons would provide a flexible encoding scheme to re-purpose visual
365 processing according to ongoing behaviour. Indeed, locomotion has been shown to
366 modulate the gain of visual responses ^{12,59} and this modulation can selectively amplify
367 specific visual features (e.g. transient ON responses ⁴²). Here we show that, in a freely
368 moving animal, modulation is richer than just locomotion, and different neurons are

369 associated diverse visuomotor contingencies, indicating higher levels of flexibility. Consistent
370 with our results, eye movements, largely suppressed in head-fixed preparations, are strongly
371 driven by changes in upward and downward facing postures in freely moving animals ⁶⁰. The
372 richer modulations observed in freely moving conditions could also be employed to support
373 coordinate transformation and spatial navigation during spontaneous exploration ^{13,61} or to
374 learn new visuomotor contingencies by gating visual inputs according to behavioural context
375 ⁶². Finally, behavioural modulation could be part of an encoding scheme that predicts
376 incoming visual inputs based on self-motion ¹⁴. These hypotheses are not mutually exclusive.

377 In summary, this study fills a gap in our understanding of how neuronal activity is coupled to
378 behaviour in the early visual system in natural unrestrained conditions. Our results indicate
379 that neuronal activity in primary visual thalamus can be flexibly modulated according to
380 movements and specific postures. The extent to which these modulations are applied to
381 different stages of the visual pathway (and to other sensory pathways) is largely unknown.
382 We believe that further investigation on this topic constitutes an important avenue for
383 future studies.

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397 **Author Contributions**

398 R.S., P.O.F., R.J.L. designed the study; R.S., P.O.F. performed experiments; R.S., P.O.F., A.S.E.,
399 A.Z. provided source codes and analysed the data; R.S., R.S.P. and R.J.L. wrote the
400 manuscript.

401

402 **Declaration of Interests**

403

404 The authors declare no competing interests.

405 **Main Text Figure Legends**

406

407 **Figure 1: Three-dimensional reconstruction and classification of postures and movements.**

408 **A)** Visualization of the eleven body landmarks applied to the animal body and the recording
409 head-stage. **B)** Representation of a selection of 8 behavioural state variables. Each vignette
410 illustrates changes in body posture and position according to an individual behavioural state
411 variable. The arrows always point towards the highest positive values. The axes indicate the
412 viewpoint (x-z for side views and x-y for top views). The other behavioural state variables not
413 represented here (dHel, dHlr, dBar, dBlr, dBlu, dRe) are obtained as temporal derivatives of
414 the associated postures. **C)** Matrix of pairwise Mutual Information between behavioural
415 state variables. Postures and movements are indicated by cyan and orange bars. **D)**
416 Hierarchical clustering for all behavioural state variables. Two levels of granularities are
417 highlighted (dashed grey lines) indicating respectively a high hierarchy (HIGH HL: postures
418 and movements, marked by cyan and yellow bars on top of the graph) and a low hierarchy
419 (LOW HL: full body movements, up/down postures, left/right postures, marked by
420 respectively by purple, orange and black bars). See also Figure S1, S2 and Video S1,S2.

421

422 **Figure 2: Upward/downward facing postures and full body movements dominate firing**

423 **rate modulation in visual thalamus in the dark. A)** Step-increases in body arch (Bar, top-left
424 panel, grey lines indicate individual events and dotted black line indicates the average
425 increase), average change in averaged firing rate (bottom-left panel) and trial-bin count
426 showing spike patterns for individual events (right panels, bin duration = 66ms). **B)** Same as
427 panel A but for a unit coupled to increases in overall motion (OM). **C)** Time series of body
428 arch (Bar) and spike counts (bin duration = 66ms) for the same unit shown in panel A. **D)**
429 Time series of overall motion (OM) and spike counts (bin duration = 66ms) for the same unit
430 shown in panel B. **E)** Results of the cross-correlation analyses (n = 96 units from 11 mice).
431 Coloured and white bars indicate the percentage of units with significant positive (coloured)
432 and negative (white) association with each behavioural state variable (Hlr: head left-right;
433 Blr: body left/right; Hel: head elevation; Bar: body arch; Re: rearing; Blu: body lunge; Lc:
434 locomotion; OM: overall motion – the other labels dHel, dBar, dRe, dBlu, dHlr, dBlr represent
435 the temporal derivatives of Hel, Bar, Re, Blu, Hlr, Blr). Grey bars indicate the overall
436 percentage of units with a significant association. Full Body movements, up/down and
437 left/right postures are highlighted by horizontal-coloured rectangles at the top. Hash
438 symbols indicate the two most prevalent variables for postures and movements (# and ##
439 respectively). **F)** Average cross-correlation across all significant units for the two most
440 prevalent variables (Bar indicated by #, OM indicated by ##; Bar+ and Bar- respectively
441 indicate units with positive and negative peak correlations). **G)** Percentage of units with a
442 significant cross-correlation peak for both up/down postures (UD) and full body movements
443 (FB) variables (striped bars), for UD only (orange) and FB only (purple). The remaining units
444 (grey) have no significant peaks for any of the remaining variables. **H)** Average magnitude
445 squared coherence (MSC, black lines) across the full dataset of recorded units (n = 96 units
446 from 11 mice) for body left/right (Blr, left panel), body arch (Bar, middle panel) and overall

447 motion (OM, right panel). Grey bars indicate the average MSC ($\pm 2SD$) obtained by random
448 shifts the behavioural state variables time series in respect to the spike patterns (n=100
449 shifts). See also Figure S3.

450 **Figure 3: Upward/downward facing postures and full body movements are the best**
451 **predictors of neuronal activity in visual thalamus in the dark.** **A)** Number of units best
452 associated with each behavioural state variable (full body movements, (FB),
453 upward/downward facing postures, (UD), and left/right postures, (LR), are highlighted by
454 colour bars at the top). Solid colour bars indicate results from Mutual Information analyses
455 while striped bars indicate results from prediction analyses. **B)** Mutual Information as
456 function of firing rate (in log units) across all cells (n=96 from 11 mice). **C)** Distribution of
457 prediction accuracy for all units recorded (left panel, n = 96 units from 11 mice; average
458 accuracy shown as vertical dashed line). The arrow indicates a unit whose prediction as
459 function of body arch (Bar) is shown on the right panel (black = original firing rate; orange =
460 predicted rate). **D)** Prediction accuracy (Mean \pm SEM, n = 96 units from 11 mice) for all units
461 as function of left/right postures (LR), up/down postures (UD), full body movements (FB)
462 and the other 7 variables. **E)** Distribution of prediction accuracy for all mice recorded (n=11).
463 The arrow indicates an animal whose prediction is shown on the right panel (prediction
464 based on n = 22 units; black = measured Bar; orange = predicted Bar). **F)** Prediction accuracy
465 (Mean \pm SEM) for all mice (n=11) as function of left/right postures (LR), up/down postures
466 (UD), full body movements (FB) and the other 7 variables. See also Figure S3.

467 **Figure 4: Single unit firing is jointly modulated by upward/downward facing postures and**
468 **full body movements in the dark.** **A)** Comparison between Mutual Information (MI)
469 conveyed by one predictor (MI1, x-axis; MI1 calculated as shuffle control, STAR Methods)
470 and two predictors (MI2, y-axis). **B)** Each horizontal bars indicates the average Mutual
471 Information (MI) between firing rates of 96 units and a pairwise combination of behavioural
472 state variables (n = 96 units from 11 mice). Bars are colour-coded according to the type of
473 variables (e.g. green for pairwise combinations of up/down postures and full body
474 movements, see legend). The inset (indicated by #) magnifies the top six pairwise
475 combinations. **C)** Mutual Information (Mean \pm SEM, n = 96 units from 11 mice) for each class
476 of predictors. **D)** Distribution of prediction accuracy for all units recorded (left panel, n = 96
477 from 11 mice; average accuracy shown as vertical dashed line). The arrow indicates a unit
478 whose prediction based on body arch (Bar) and overall motion (OM) is shown on the right
479 panel (black = original firing rate; green = predicted rate). **E)** Z-score transformed firing rate
480 (color coded) as function of body arch (Bar) and overall motion (OM). The units are divided
481 into “look-up” and “look-down” units. The two poses at the top of each panel represent the
482 extreme upper and lower quantile for body arch (Bar). **F)** Z-score transformed firing rates
483 (mean \pm SEM, n = 52, 44, respectively look-up and look-down units) as function of Body Arch
484 (Bar, top panel) and overall motions (OM, bottom panel). See also Figure S3.

485 **Figure 5: Modulation of single unit activity by behavioural state is maintained and**
486 **amplified by ambient illumination.** **A)** Mutual Information (mean \pm SEM, n = 75 units from 8
487 mice) for each motor state variable in dark and illuminated environments. **B)** Number of
488 units best associated with each behavioural state variable according to our Mutual

489 Information analysis (full body movements, FB, up/down postures, UD, and left/right
490 postures, LR, are highlighted by colour rectangles at the top). **C)** Distribution of prediction
491 accuracy for all units recorded (left panel, n = 75 from 8 mice; average accuracy shown as
492 vertical dashed line). The arrow indicates a unit whose prediction based on body arch (Bar)
493 and overall motion (OM) is shown on the right panel (black = original firing rate; green =
494 predicted rate). **D)** Z-score transformed firing rate (color coded) as function of body arch
495 (Bar) and overall motion (OM). The units are divided into “look-up” and “look-down” units.
496 The two poses at the top of each panel represent the extreme upper and lower quantile for
497 body arch (Bar). **E)** Z-score transformed firing rates (mean±SEM, n = 36, 39, respectively
498 look-up and look-down units) as function of body arch (Bar, top panel) and overall motions
499 (OM, bottom panel). **F)** Two example units in which we calculated cross-correlation (CC) of
500 firing activity with body arch (Bar, left panels) and overall movements (OM, right panels). A
501 strong similarity between CC calculated under dark (black lines) and light conditions
502 (coloured lines) is revealed for both units. **G)** Pearson’s correlation between cross-correlation
503 estimates in dark and light conditions (ρ_{CC}). The average Pearson’s correlation (ρ_{CC} data) is
504 significantly larger than values expected by randomly shuffling the pairing between units in
505 dark and light (ρ_{CC} shuffle, n = 10000 shuffles). See also Figure S4.

506

507

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509

510

511 **STAR Methods**

512 **RESOURCE AVAILABILITY**

513

514 **Lead Contact**

515

516 Further information and requests for resources, reagents or raw data should be directed to
517 and will be fulfilled by the Lead Contact, Riccardo Storchi
518 (riccardo.storchi@manchester.ac.uk)

519

520 **Materials Availability**

521

522 This study did not generate new unique reagents.

523

524 **Data and Code Availability**

525

526 Data and source codes are available at <https://osf.io/q6cwp/>. For additional information and
527 support please contact riccardo.storchi@manchester.ac.uk.

528

529 **EXPERIMENTAL MODEL AND SUBJECT DETAILS**

530

531 **Animals**

532

533 Experiments were conducted on 12 adult, male C57BL/6J mice (Charles River). All mice were
534 initially stored in cages of 5 individuals and housed individually after surgical implantation of
535 the chronic electrode. Animals were provided with food and water *ad libitum* throughout
536 their life and kept on a 12:12 light dark cycle.

537

538 **Ethical Statement**

539

540 Experiments were conducted in accordance with the Animals, Scientific Procedures Act of
541 1986 (United Kingdom) and approved by the University of Manchester ethical review
542 committee.

543

544

545 **METHOD DETAILS**

546

547 **Recovery Surgery**

548

549 Throughout the procedure mice were anaesthetised with isoflurane (95/5% Oxygen/CO2
550 mix; flow rate: 0.5 – 1.0L/min). Concentrations of 4 – 5% and 0.5 – 1.5% were used
551 respectively for induction and maintenance of anaesthesia. The level of anaesthesia was
552 verified by the lack of withdrawal reflex. During the surgery animal's body temperature was
553 automatically maintained at 37°C by a heating mat and animal's eyes were protected from

554 drying out by eye drops. Once placed in the stereotaxic frame (Narishige, Japan), the animal
555 fur was trimmed and 1% EMLA cream applied topically to the surrounding skin. An incision
556 was made to expose a skull surface and set stereotactic *bregma* point, craniotomy and
557 screws coordinates. Next, two slotted cheese machine screws (M1.6x2.0mm, Precision Tools,
558 UK) were inserted respectively into the parietal, and interparietal plates to act as anchors for
559 the dental cement and for electrical grounding of the electrode. After craniotomy the
560 electrode was inserted into the dLGN (coordinates from *bregma*: 2.0-2.5mm medial-lateral,
561 2.3-2.5 mm rostro-caudal) at a depth of 2.8mm from the brain surface. To assess electrode
562 placement we monitored light responses during surgical implantation of the electrode
563 (Figure 5D). Light-curing cement (X-tra base, VO64434-A, VOCO) was applied to seal the
564 implant. After surgery, the mouse was released from the ear bars and allowed to recover in a
565 single-housed heated cage. Analgesia was provided with an intramuscular injection of
566 0.05mg/kg buprenorphine. After the procedure the animal was allowed to recover in a
567 single-housed home-cage for a minimum of six days prior to experimentation. After all data
568 were collected animals were perfused and histological post-mortem anatomy was
569 performed to confirm electrode placement (Figure S5E).

570

571 **Experimental Set-Up**

572 A detailed description of the experimental set-up for behavioural recordings is provided in ⁶³.
573 The animals were recorded in a square open field arena (dimensions: 30cm x 30 cm, Figure
574 S1A). Behavioural recordings were acquired with 4 programmable cameras (Chameleon 3
575 from Point Grey; frame rate = 15Hz) equipped with infrared cut-on filters (cut-on at 720 nm,
576 Edmund Optics, #65-796) to isolate light in the infra-red range. Neuronal recordings were
577 performed via 16 channel electrodes (Neuronexus; model: A4x4-3mm-50-125-177; package:
578 CM16) with a TBSI W16 wireless acquisition system (Triangular BioSystems; sampling rate =
579 30 kHz). Frame acquisition, controlled via Psychopy (version 1.82.01, ⁶⁴), was synchronized
580 with acquisition of neuronal data via an Arduino Uno board (www.arduino.cc). This board
581 delivered a common electrical trigger to the cameras and the electrophysiological
582 acquisition system.

583 The experiments were performed in light-tight cubicles that are part of the circadian
584 facilities at the University of Manchester. Light-tightness is ensured by separating the
585 experimental room from external light sources (such as windows) through 3 sealed doors
586 that connect the cubicles to a corridor, the corridor to an antechamber and the
587 antechamber to the rest of the facility. These measures were sufficient to bring light levels
588 below the detection of any of our light meters (1.7nW; MACAM PM203 Optical Power Meter
589 and SpectroCAL MKII Spectroradiometer) and of a dark-adapted human observer.

590 **Behavioural Protocol**

591 Naïve animals were briefly anaesthetised (~2 minutes) with 3% isoflurane in order to
592 connect the electrode head-stage. They were gently positioned at the centre of the arena
593 and allowed plenty of time to recover from the anaesthesia. After the animals expressed
594 sustained exploration of the arena (typically ~20 minutes after being placed in the arena) the
595 experiment started. Animals were not specifically trained and freely explored the arena

596 throughout the duration of the experiment (typically ~45 minutes). Arena illumination was
 597 through a rear projection screen mounted over the arena and provided excitation of
 598 $4.08 \cdot 10^{10}$, $1.65 \cdot 10^{13}$, $1.94 \cdot 10^{13}$ and $2.96 \cdot 10^{13}$ photon/cm²/s respectively to S-cone opsin,
 599 Melanopsin, Rhodopsin and M-cone opsin. To calculate photon flux we weighted the
 600 spectral irradiance of our illumination by the pigment spectral efficiency estimated by using
 601 Govardovskii nomograms⁶⁵. We then multiplied this by spectral lens transmission, measured
 602 in⁶⁶, to account for the filtering effect of the mouse lens that attenuates light in the UV and
 603 near-UV band. During recordings in the dark, brief steps of light (0.66-1.33 seconds) were
 604 provided to test for visual responses. During recordings under steady illumination brief steps
 605 of dark (0.66-1.33 seconds) were also delivered. Video recordings were performed in epochs
 606 of 15-24 seconds, each separated by 30-40 seconds.

607

608 **QUANTIFICATION AND STATISTICAL ANALYSIS**

609

610 All analysis except the predictive modelling were performed in MATLAB (Natick,
 611 Massachusetts, USA) by using custom-made code. Predictive modelling of neuronal and
 612 behavioural data was performed in Python and based on xgboost library⁶⁷.

613

614 **Reconstruction of 3D Poses**

615

616 An initial 3D reconstruction of the mouse body was obtained by triangulating body
 617 landmarks from the four cameras (see body landmarks in Figure 1A). The four-camera
 618 system was calibrated as previously described³⁴. Tracking of body landmarks from individual
 619 cameras was performed with DeepLabCut⁶⁸. The algorithm was trained with ~1000
 620 manually annotated images and ran on a dedicated Ubuntu machine equipped with a Titan
 621 RTX GPU (Nvidia, Santa Clara, California, USA). The initial 3D reconstruction was
 622 contaminated with missing data and outliers, typically due to occluded body points. In order
 623 to correct the 3D reconstruction we modified a previously developed algorithm³⁴. We first
 624 estimated a Statistical Shape Model (SSM,⁶⁹) from a dataset of 350 manually re-annotated
 625 3D poses. The poses were initially aligned by used Procrustes Superimposition (with scale
 626 parameter = 1). The SSM was then estimated by applying Probabilistic Principal Component
 627 Analysis (PPCA,⁷⁰; MATLAB function: *ppca*). The SSM allowed us to express the 3D pose of
 628 the animal position as

629

$$\mathbf{X} = \left(\bar{\mathbf{X}} + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{eigenposes}} \mathbf{P}_i b_i \right) \mathbf{R} + \mathbf{T} \quad (1)$$

630 Where: \mathbf{X} is an $N_p \times 3$ matrix representing the 3D pose for given frame (N_p is the number of
 631 body landmarks); $\bar{\mathbf{X}}$ is the mean pose; \mathbf{P}_i and b_i represent respectively the i^{th} eigenpose
 632 obtained by training the SSM and its score (the shape parameter); \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{T} are respectively
 633 the 3×3 rotation and $N_p \times 3$ translation matrices that map the animal's position in the

634 experimental environment. Note that is \mathbf{T} obtained as $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{t} \otimes \mathbf{1}$ where $\mathbf{t} = [t_x, t_y, t_z]$ is
 635 the 3D translation vector and $\mathbf{1}$ is an $N_p \times 1$ all-ones vector. To obtain a robust 3D
 636 reconstruction we minimised, as function of $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{T})$, the following cost function

637

$$C(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{T}) = \sigma^{-2} \left\| \mathbf{X} - \left(\bar{\mathbf{X}} + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{eigenposes}} b_i \mathbf{P}_i \right) \mathbf{R} - \mathbf{T} \right\|_F^2 + \alpha \sum_{i=1}^{N_{eigenposes}} \frac{b_i^2}{\lambda_i} \quad (2)$$

638 Where: σ^2 represents the noise term obtained from the PPCA, λ_i the eigenvalue associated
 639 with the i^{th} eigenpose and α , the regularization parameter, was set at 0.01. Outliers in a
 640 pose were flagged when the $C > inv(X^2(3N_p))$, with N_p indicting the number of body
 641 landmarks. When this happened, we removed the body landmark associated with largest
 642 value of C , reduced N_p by 1, and recalculated C . This operation was performed iteratively
 643 until $C < inv(X^2(3N_p))$. Then, in order to fill-up missing values and correct the remaining
 644 3D coordinates, we recalculated \mathbf{X} as in equation (1), by using $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{T})$ values obtained from
 645 the minimization of equation (2) and $\bar{\mathbf{X}}, \mathbf{P}$ provided by the SSM.

646

647 **Quantification of Behavioural State Variables**

648

649 Quantification of behavioural state variables was based on 3D data after applying the
 650 reconstruction algorithms described above. Head elevation (Hel) was calculated as the angle
 651 between the nose and the neck landmarks. Head left and right turns (Hlr) as the angle
 652 between midline and nose. Body arch (Bar), body left and right turns (Blr), and body lounge
 653 (Blu) corresponded to the shape parameters associated respectively with first, second and
 654 third eigenposes. These definitions (e.g. body arch) were based on visual inspection of the
 655 videos in which we visualised the full body changes in shapes along each eigenpose (see
 656 Video S2). Rearing corresponded to the z-coordinate of the translation matrix \mathbf{T} . Locomotion
 657 (Lc) was calculated as Euclidean distance on the x-y axis of the body centre between two
 658 consecutive frames. The body centre in each frame was defined by the values of the
 659 translation vector \mathbf{t} (see above). Overall motion (OM) was defined as the Euclidean across of
 660 all body points between two consecutive frames. All behavioural state variables were then
 661 transformed into z-scores for all further analyses.

662

663 **Hierarchical Clustering**

664

665 Hierarchical agglomerative clustering across all behavioural state variables was applied to
 666 the Mutual Information matrix (Fig.1D). The hierarchical trees were created by using nearest
 667 distance method (MATLAB function: *linkage*, metric: *weighted*).

668

669 **Pre-processing of Neuronal Data**

670 Action potentials (typically >50 μV , see Figure 5A) were extracted from the continuous, high-
671 pass filtered signals (low cut-off at 250 Hz) by using Offline Sorter (version 3). Noise artifacts
672 were then removed. Then individual units were first sorted by combining template sorting
673 method (Valley Seek) with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) in Offline Sorter software
674 (Plexon, USA) and next manually adjusted. Inter-spike interval histograms were inspected to
675 make sure that no spike events occurred during the refractory period (defined at 1ms
676 duration). When there was more than one cluster on the channel (15 channels with 1 cluster
677 and 58 channels with >1 cluster were spike sorted), reliable single unit isolation was
678 confirmed by a MANOVA test (Offline Sorter). Signal-to noise ratio (SNR) was then calculated
679 for each unit and only units with $\text{SNR} > 1.5$ were kept for further analysis (Figure S5B-C). In
680 order to avoid double counting the same unit from different channels we merged units that
681 shared > 50% spikes timestamps from pairs of neighbouring channels (this only happened
682 twice).

683

684 **Cross-correlation Analyses**

685

686 Cross-correlation between spike counts and behavioural state variables was estimated after
687 removal of the mean from each signal. In order to test for statistical significance we
688 estimated a null-distribution by using a shuffling procedure. The association between spikes
689 and behavioural state variables was broken by dividing spike counts into epochs and
690 randomly permuting the order of such epochs. This operation was repeated 1000 times in
691 order to generate the null-distribution. Original cross-correlation was deemed significant
692 when at least one of its value (range [-2,+2] seconds; time-bin = 0.0667 seconds) was
693 outside a [0.0005,0.9995] confidence interval.

694

695 **Mutual Information Analyses**

696

697 Prior to estimation, continuous behavioural state variables were transformed into discrete
698 variables by applying quantile discretization. Probability distributions were then estimated
699 from the frequency histograms of each signal. These distributions were used to obtain
700 response and noise entropies, respectively calculated as

701

$$H(R) = - \sum_{g \in G} p(r) \log_2 p(r)$$

$$H(R|S) = - \sum_{g \in G, s \in S} p(r, s) \log_2 p(r|s)$$

702

703 Where: r indicates spike counts and s indicates the values of the behavioural state variables.
704 Throughout this study we used a time-bin duration of 0.67 seconds for spike counts. Both
705 entropy terms were corrected for the sampling bias by using quadratic extrapolation as in
706 [63]. Shannon's Mutual Information (MI) was then calculated as $MI = H(R) - H(R|S)$.

707 When comparing MI obtained from one vs two behavioural state variables (as e.g. in **Figure**
708 **4A**), we adopted the following strategy. First MI was estimated for two behavioural state
709 variables as described above. Then, MI for single variables was estimated from the same two
710 variables but by previously shuffling the order of one or of the other variable. Finally, the
711 largest MI obtained by shuffling was taken as estimate of MI for an individual variable.

712

713 **Predictive Modelling Analyses**

714 Prediction of spike counts based on behavioural state variables was performed with eXtreme
715 Gradient Boosting (XGBoost, ^{35,67}; parameters: learning rate = 0.025; number of boosting
716 iterations = 500; evaluation metric: log-likelihood loss; subsample = 1; maximum depth = 3;
717 gamma = 1; tree method: gpu_hist). This method has been shown to outperform spike count
718 predictions obtained with more standard approaches based on Generalized Linear Models
719 ³⁶. Prediction of behavioural state variables from spike counts was also based on the same
720 XGB models. All datasets were bisected into two equal parts that were used for training and
721 cross-validation. Prediction performance on the cross-validation set were measured as
722 Pearson's linear correlation between predicted and original firing rate. Throughout this study
723 we used a time-bin duration of 0.67 seconds for spike counts. For prediction of spike counts,
724 in order to test for the possibility that positive correlations were obtained purely by chance,
725 we repeated this analysis by shifting the behavioural state variables. Shifting was obtained
726 by splitting the behavioural state time series into two equally long epochs and inverting the
727 order of those epochs. In this way the association of these time series with spike counts was
728 abolished while the temporal structure of those series was preserved.

729

730 **Clustering of Firing Rate Histograms**

731 We use Newman's algorithm for community detection, that maximizes network modularity
732 ³⁷. The higher the modularity the better the clustering. For our data each unit of the network
733 is a bivariate firing rate histogram calculated as function of body arch and overall motion.
734 The adjacency matrix for the network was based on Spearman's correlation between firing
735 rate histograms. Each pair of units was considered connected when their pairwise
736 correlation was above the median the correlation distribution, The algorithm works by
737 iteratively bisecting the network ³⁷. Therefore it first considers the whole network and
738 bisects it according to the first eigenvector of the modularity matrix (eq 3 in Newman 2006
739 ³⁷). Then it considers each partition and perform further bisections. The algorithm
740 terminates when it cannot find any further bisection that would increase network
741 modularity.

742

743 **Supplemental Video Legends**

744 **Video S1: Three-Dimensional reconstruction of freely moving behaviour. Related to Figure**
745 **1.** Representative movie illustrating 3D reconstruction of behaviour. Top and bottom left
746 panels show the same animal from two camera views. Top and bottom right panels show the
747 3D reconstruction from side and top views.

748 **Video S2: Animated illustration of behavioural state variables. Related to Figure 1.**
749 Illustration of changes in head postures (head elevation, head left/right), full body postures
750 (captured by the first 3 eigenposes of the Statistical Shape Model), locomotion and rearing.
751 Left and right panels show respectively top and side views of the animal body.

752

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754

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924 **Figures**

925 **Figure 1**

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937 Figure 5

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940 **Supplementary Figures Legend**

941 Figure S1: A) A pictures of the experimental apparatus (left panel). The arena is placed in the
942 centre and imaged by four overhead cameras (indicated by red arrows). A representative
943 frame simultaneously acquired by the 4 cameras is shown (right panel). B-C) Same as Figure
944 1C-D but for animals recorded in the dark. D-E) Same as Figure 1C-D but for animals recorded
945 under photopic light.

946 Figure S2: A) Representative time series for a selection of behavioural state variables (head
947 elevation, Hel, body arch, Bar, rearing, Re, body lunge, Blu, head left/right, Hlr, body left/right,
948 Blr, locomotion, Lc, overall motion, OM – the variables not shown are simply obtained as time
949 derivative of the postures). B) Poses from six frames (indicated in panel A by vertical blue
950 lines) are shown from side and top view. C) Average body arch (Bar), rearing (Re) and head
951 elevation (Hel) at the onset of a rearing event (detected at time 0). Note that body arch and
952 head elevation precede rearing. D) Average body arch (Bar) and head elevation (Hel) at the
953 onset of an upward head movement (detected at time = 0). E) Same as panel D but for head
954 left/right (Hlr) and body left/right (Blr) measured at onset of a leftward head movement. F)
955 Average overall motion (OM) and locomotion (Lc) at the onset of a rearing event.

956 Figure S3: A) Distribution of mean (left panel) and peak firing rates (right panel) for our
957 dataset (n = 96 units from 11 mice). B) Relation between mean and peak firing rates for the
958 same dataset shown in panel A. C) Paired difference in prediction accuracy (measured as
959 Person's ρ) between original and shifted predictors (n = 96 units for 11 mice). D) Comparison
960 between prediction accuracy obtained with one variable (x-axis) and two variables (y-axis). E) Each
961 horizontal bars indicates the average prediction accuracy for pairwise combinations of behavioural
962 state variables (n = 96 units from 11 mice). Bars are colour-coded according to the type of variables
963 (e.g. green for pairwise combinations of up/down postures and full body movements, see legend). The
964 inset (indicated by #) magnifies the top six pairwise combinations. F) Prediction accuracy (Mean \pm SEM,
965 n = 96 units from 11 mice) for each class of predictors. G) Z-score transformed firing rate (color
966 coded) as function of head elevation (Hel) and overall motion (OM). The units are divided into
967 "look-up" and "look-down" units. The two poses at the top of each panel represent the
968 extreme upper and lower quantile for head elevation. H) Z-score transformed firing rates
969 (mean \pm SEM, n = 52, 45, respectively look-up and look-down units) as function of head
970 elevation (Hel, top panel) and overall motions (OM, bottom panel). I-J) Same as panels G-H
971 but for rearing (Re) instead of head elevation.

972 Figure S4: A) Prediction accuracy (mean \pm SEM, n = 75 units from 8 mice) for each behavioural
973 state variable in dark and illuminated environments (indicated respectively by black and
974 coloured bars). B) Number of units best associated with each behavioural state variable
975 according to our prediction analysis (full body movements, FB, upward/downward facing
976 postures, UD, and left/right postures, LR, are highlighted by colour rectangles at the top). C)
977 Comparison between Mutual Information (MI) conveyed by one predictor (x-axis; MI
978 calculated as shuffle control) and two predictors (y-axis). D) Each horizontal bar indicates the
979 average MI between firing rates (n = 75 units from 8 mice) and a pairwise combination of
980 behavioural state variables. Bars are colour-coded according to the type of variables (e.g.
981 green for up/down postures and full body movements, UD+FB, see legend). The inset
982 (indicated by #) magnifies the top six pairwise combinations. E) Mutual Information
983 (Mean \pm SEM, n = 75 units from 8 mice) for each class of predictors. F-H) Same as panels C-E
984 but here we calculated prediction accuracy instead of Mutual Information. I) Distribution of
985 prediction accuracy for all mice (n = 11; average accuracy shown as vertical dashed line). The
986 arrow indicates an animal whose prediction based on body arch (Bar) is shown on the right

987 panel (black = original firing rate; orange = predicted rate). J) Average prediction accuracy
988 (Mean±SEM) for all animals (n=8) as function of left/right postures (LR), up/down postures
989 (UD), full body movements (FB) and other variables (OT, which indicates the remaining 7
990 variables).

991 Supplementary Figure 5: A) Representative extracellular recording. Spikes detected are
992 indicated by orange dots and three of them magnified for visual inspection (see insets 1-3).
993 B) Representative sample of recorded units. Signal-to-Noise ratio (SNR) is reported at the top
994 of each panel. Only units with SNR>1.5 were used for further analyses (here we excluded the
995 first unit on the left since SNR=1.34). C) Distribution of SNR across our dataset (black vertical
996 line indicates the threshold for inclusion). D) Visual responses from extracellular recordings
997 at the end of surgical implantation of the recording electrodes. Yellow shading indicates the
998 epoch in which full-field light stimulation was on (light onset at time 0, stimulus duration =
999 0.5s). Top-left panel shows the multichannel electrode layout. E) Histological verification of
1000 electrode placement in which fluorescent trace indicate the position of the rostral shank (left
1001 panel). Right panel shows the estimated position of isolated single units (blue dots) along
1002 rostro-caudal axis.

1003

A

DARK

B

C

LIGHT

D

E

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